

QUIZ**LAST NAME: EMEH****FIRST NAME: KELECHI****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. What is the most appropriate tool that researchers, academia and others use in planning long reports for academic purpose?**
 - A detailed sketch.
 - Storyboard.¹**
 - A basic Outline.
 - Ordinary plan.

- 2. What are the two most important things to consider while presenting a graphic representation of complex numbers in a table, graph or chart?**
 - Use only figures to present table, graph and chart.

1. Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 22.

- Frame the table, graph or chart so readers understand it and equally demonstrate the relationship in the table, graph or chart.²**
 - Make the table, graph and charts very fanciful.
 - Use one type of table, graph and chart to present all figures.
3. **What are the two important components for citing online sources?**
- Include only whether the material was obtained as print or online source.
 - Include full facts of publication date in addition to a URL.³**
 - Include full date for sourcing material and name of author.
 - Include information on type of online source (e.g., journal, book, website).
4. **To begin the process of writing a successful dissertation, a researcher needs to create to important things:**
- Both mental and physical workspaces.⁴**
 - Create table of content and title cover page.
 - Apply for grants to enable the writing of the dissertation.
 - Meet your supervisor to discuss the content of the dissertation.
5. **The choice of the research approach is directly tied to two factors. Kindly names these factors.**

2. Ibid., 56.

3. Turabian, 88.

4. Linda Bloomberg and Maria Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage publication), 3.

- Research Topic and author.
 - Research institution and funding.
 - Research problem and purpose.**⁵
 - Research problem and author.
6. **Academic or scholarly writing is, in essence, a writing that has three key characteristics. These are:**
- Ambiguity, high level grammar, punctuation marks.
 - Clarity, coherence, cohesiveness.**⁶
 - Spacing, use Turabian style for all documents, write sub-urban English.
 - Use scientific language, use lots of charts, graphs and tables, apply religious texts.
7. **In seeking a research topic, a scholar should focus on:**
- Advancing knowledge or understanding of a practice of phenomenon.**⁷
 - Any grandiose ideas that the scholar wants to pursue.
 - Any topic that is fun to research and write.
 - Advancing topics that are broad and ambitious.
8. **Researchers normally ask three types of questions. What are these types of questions?**

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, 7.

⁶ Ibid., 22.

⁷ Ibid., 5.

- Conceptual questions, practical questions, applied questions.**⁸
 - Religious questions, ethnic questions and nationality.
 - Social questions, political questions and economic questions.
 - Good questions, annoying questions and difficult questions.
9. **The secondary legislation in European Union is considered as legal acts adopted under the Treaties. These secondary legislations comprise chiefly:**
- Regulations, decisions, Directives.**⁹
 - Articles of association, policies, and guidelines.
 - Decisions, instructions, and resolutions.
 - Directives, meeting minutes, communiqués.
10. **In drafting EU legislation or any document for public use; the author should consider the use of:**
- European Union English guide style.**¹⁰
 - International writing style only.
 - Turabian rule of style.
 - African rule of style.

⁸ Turabian, 15.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2011), 56,

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 1.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Linda Bloomberg, and Maria Volpe. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.